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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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FORMATION OF ENVIRONMENTAL PROTECTION AND “GREEN” ECONOMY CONCEPTS AMONG SCHOOL-AGE YOUTH

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Abstract: The article examines certain issues related to the formation of concepts on environmental protection and the “green” economy among school-age youth.

Key words: environmental protection, green economy, environmental legal consciousness, environmental legal education, biological diversity, flora and fauna, environmental education, environmental upbringing.

Annotatsiya: Maqolada maktab yoshidagi yoshlar orasida atrof-muhitni muhofaza qilish va “yashil iqtisodiyot” tushunchalarini shakllantirish bilan bog‘liq ayrim masalalar ko‘rib chiqilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: atrof-muhitni muhofaza qilish, yashil iqtisodiyot, ekologik huquqiy ong, ekologik huquqiy ta‘lim, biologik xilma-xillik, flora va fauna, ekologik ta‘lim, ekologik tarbiya.

Аннотация: В статье рассматриваются отдельные вопросы, связанные с формированием представлений об охране окружающей среды и “зелёной экономике” среди молодёжи школьного возраста.

Ключевые слова: охрана окружающей среды, зелёная экономика, экологическое правосознание, экологическое правовое образование, биологическое разнообразие, флора и фауна, экологическое образование, экологическое воспитание.

INTRODUCTION

Today in our country, the formation of concepts related to environmental protection and the “green” economy among school-age youth is being carried out in accordance with contemporary requirements and international standards.

Indeed, the fact that the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, in his address to the Oliy Majlis on 20 November 2024, declared 2025 in Uzbekistan as the “Year of Environmental Protection and the ‘Green’ Economy” is of exceptional importance, as this initiative directly reflects the demands of the globalization process and the “green” economy. In this regard, the updated Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan and other subordinate normative legal acts are being adopted.

It should be noted that Article 4 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Environmental Protection” stipulates the “obligatory teaching of ecology in all types of educational institutions,” and the main objective of environmental education is to form a conscious attitude toward environmental protection issues among all layers of the population, including students of general secondary schools and technical colleges, as well as higher education students.

In this field, our school-age youth must understand that, in accordance with the Laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Education” and “On Environmental Protection,” adopted by the Legislative Chamber on 19 May 2020 and approved by the Senate on 7 August 2020, one of the key tasks of the Concept for the Development of Environmental Education in the System of Continuous Education is to define the basic principles of environmental education, to consistently and gradually implement them in the educational process, and, on this basis, to raise the effectiveness of environmental education to a new stage.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Issues related to environmental protection and the formation of “green economy” concepts among young people have been widely studied by both international and national researchers. In recent decades, environmental education has become one of the key directions of sustainable development policies, and many scholars have emphasized the importance of raising environmental awareness among younger generations.

According to the studies of David Orr (1992), environmental education should not only provide ecological knowledge but also develop environmentally responsible behavior and values among learners. Orr argues that ecological literacy is an essential component of modern education and plays a significant role in preparing young people for sustainable living.

Stephen Sterling (2001) highlighted the importance of integrating sustainability principles into educational systems. He emphasized that environmental education should encourage critical thinking, responsible decision-making, and active participation in solving environmental problems. His research demonstrated that sustainable development education contributes to the formation of environmentally conscious citizens.

Research conducted by UNESCO (2020) also underlines that environmental education and education for sustainable development are effective tools for developing environmental culture, ecological responsibility, and awareness of global environmental challenges among school-age youth. UNESCO recommends integrating environmental topics into all levels of education to strengthen learners' understanding of ecological issues.

Among scholars of the Commonwealth of Independent States, N.F. Reimers and V.A. Yasvin made significant contributions to the development of environmental education theory. Their studies emphasized the formation of environmental consciousness, ecological culture, and responsible attitudes toward nature through educational activities.

In Uzbekistan, environmental education and environmental culture have been investigated by several researchers. Their studies focus on improving ecological awareness among students, strengthening environmental legal education, and developing environmentally responsible behavior. Particular attention has been paid to integrating environmental education into the system of continuous education and supporting state initiatives aimed at environmental protection and sustainable development.

The analysis of the reviewed literature shows that environmental education, ecological culture, and “green economy” concepts are closely interconnected. However, the issue of forming comprehensive concepts of environmental protection and the “green economy” among school-age youth within the context of modern environmental challenges requires further research and practical improvement. Therefore, the present study focuses on examining the pedagogical and social aspects of developing environmental awareness and “green economy” concepts among young people.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study employed theoretical analysis, comparative analysis, and document review methods. National legislation, presidential decrees, government resolutions, international environmental documents, and scientific literature related to environmental protection and the green economy were analyzed. The collected materials were examined to identify effective approaches for developing environmental awareness and green economy concepts among school-age youth.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Therefore, it is necessary to explain to young people, within the scope of the activities being carried out to improve the quality of life of the population in Uzbekistan, the measures that are specifically aimed at improving the environmental situation in our country. In particular, the Presidential Decree of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated 30 October 2019 “On the Concept for Environmental Protection of the Republic of Uzbekistan for the Period up to 2030” and the Decree dated 30 December 2021 “On Measures to Accelerate Landscaping Work, Ensure More Effective Protection of Trees and Organize Their Protection” define the implementation of the nationwide project “Green Space,” which provides for the protection of environmental objects (air, water, land, soil, subsoil, biodiversity, and protected natural territories) from human and other negative impacts, ensuring their quality, and improving mechanisms for reducing the ecological load on settlements under conditions of rapid expansion of industrial production and urbanization.

It is also necessary to provide school-age youth with a broad understanding of the most important international document adopted to improve the quality of life of the world's population—the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), adopted by the United Nations (UN) in 2015, which consist of 17 interrelated goals aimed at solving the main problems facing humanity. In addition, young people should know that, in Uzbekistan, an action plan has been developed to accelerate the implementation of national goals and tasks in the field of

sustainable development for the period up to 2030, within which 16 national sustainable development goals and 125 tasks have been identified. It is noteworthy that among the national goals there are tasks such as adopting urgent measures to combat climate change and its consequences, protecting and restoring terrestrial ecosystems and promoting their rational use, ensuring the rational use of forests, combating desertification, halting and reversing land degradation, and preventing the loss of biodiversity.

Likewise, it is advisable that young people know and incorporate into their activities the fact that the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan approved, by Resolution No. 434 of 27 May 2019, the “Concept for the Development of Environmental Education in the Republic of Uzbekistan.”

School-age youth must realize that the implementation of the nationwide project “Green Space” in the Republic—aimed at protecting and restoring ecosystems, accelerating landscaping work, and expanding green areas—is a crucial step. Within the framework of this project, it is planned to increase green areas in the regions from the current 8 percent to 30 percent by planting 200 million tree and shrub seedlings annually, and it is essential that students understand the significance of this initiative. In this sense, it is commendable that extensive work is being carried out on tree planting in all cities and villages, and students must feel personally responsible for the care of trees planted every autumn and spring and for their subsequent condition.

At this point, school-age youth should also visualize the fact that in recent years climate change has been observed in Uzbekistan, including an increase in average annual temperatures and a tendency toward intensifying seasonal droughts, which is negatively influenced by the desiccation of the Aral Sea. To mitigate the consequences of this negative impact, a number of measures have been developed and are being implemented by our state, including the creation of an additional 500 thousand hectares of green areas on the dried bottom of the Aral Sea, increasing their total area to 2.5 million hectares or 78 percent of the territory by the end of 2026, and implementing projects worth 300 million US dollars in the Aral Sea region under the programs of the Green Climate Fund and the Global Environment Facility aimed at biodiversity conservation, climate change mitigation, and prevention of land degradation. It is a matter of great responsibility for young people to be aware of these measures.

It should be emphasized that today processes of integration of all levels of social consciousness and forms of culture within the framework of environmental interests are intensifying. In such a situation, when explaining to school-age youth the issue of environmental protection, it is necessary to show that the process of developing environmental culture should be analyzed by distinguishing two interrelated but relatively independent directions.

First, on the basis of a system of theoretical environmental knowledge, it is necessary to organize the practical activity of school-age youth in transforming and mastering nature through the rational organization of production, technology, and technical progress.

Second, on the basis of historical environmental experience and with the help of social institutions of environmental education and upbringing, it is essential to develop environmental consciousness, thinking, and worldview among school-age youth. Harmonious development of these directions, grounded in universal interests, ultimately plays a major role in forming active environmental culture and in students’ participation in environmental protection activities.

It is clear that the future of our planet depends on the environmental culture of the younger generation. The systematic organization of the process of environmental knowledge, consciousness, and culture, as well as environmental education and upbringing among school-age youth—while attracting advanced innovative technologies in the field of ecology and continuously improving this sphere—is a requirement of our time, which aims to increase young people’s knowledge and skills in loving Mother Nature and protecting it as the apple of their eye. School-age youth must not forget the invaluable role of broad public participation in the implementation of these noble tasks.

In general, improving and applying in practice appropriate means and methods in the education system on the basis of a scientific understanding of the relationship between nature and society is a necessary condition for the development of environmental culture, and it remains an urgent task to ensure the harmonious development of all directions, methods, and means of education and upbringing.

School-age youth should also know that, by the Decree of the Head of our State dated 4 October 2019, the Strategy for the Transition of the Republic of Uzbekistan to a “Green” Economy for 2019–2030, aimed at integrating climate change issues into the sustainable development of the national economy, was approved, and they should be aware of its main tasks. These include increasing the energy efficiency of the economy and the rational use of natural resources; introducing “green” criteria into priority areas and expenditures of public investment; ensuring state incentives for projects implementing the principles of the “green” economy; training personnel for the “green” economy; and developing international cooperation in the field of the “green” economy, among others.

In this regard, school-age youth should realize that the “green economy” rests on three theoretical premises: first, that it is impossible to infinitely expand human impact within a limited space; second, that ever-growing consumption demand cannot be satisfied under conditions of limited resources; and third, that all natural phenomena on Earth are interconnected, which is why it is essential to know and follow the requirements of environmental protection and the “green” economy. From this point of view, the development of the “green economy” is one of the most pressing issues of today.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the prudent attitude of our ancestors toward environmental protection and natural resources should always serve as our fundamental life principle, and we must take them as an example. Protecting nature helps to prevent threats to human life, serves as a key factor in the development of our future, and makes a major contribution to preserving natural wealth. Therefore, environmental protection is a human duty for all of us.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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